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PROGNOSTIC VALUE OF OSTEOPROTEGERIN FOR ESTIMATION OF CARDIOVASCULAR RISK IN PATIENTS WITH LONG-STANDING TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS

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ПРОГНОСТИЧНА СТОЙНОСТ НА ОСТЕОПРОТЕГЕРИН ЗА ОЦЕНКА НА СЪРДЕЧНО-СЪДОВ РИСК ПРИ ПАЦИЕНТИ С ДЪЛГОГОДИШЕН ЗАХАРЕН ДИАБЕТ ТИП 1

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Abstract.

Background: Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a major complication in patients with long-standing type 1 diabetes (T1D). Osteoprotegerin (OPG) has been proposed as a biomarker for cardiovascular risk (CVR), though its utility in this context requires further evaluation. This study **aimed** to assess the prognostic significance of OPG in CVR estimation among T1D patients using specific CVR assessment tools. **Patients and Methods:** This prospective case-control study includes 183 participants: 124 with T1D (53.2% men, aged 42.7 ± 10.4 years, diabetes duration 25.3 ± 8.2 years) and 59 healthy controls (54.1% men, aged 45.1 ± 9.1 years). Serum OPG levels were determined via ELISA; CRP – immune-turbidimetric method (Advia chemistry 1800); HbA1C (%) – immuno-inhibition assay (ADVIA chemistry 1800); AlbU (mg/l) – immuno-turbidimetric analysis (Olympus AU600). CVR evaluation tools: STENO Type 1 Risk Engine (ST1RE) and ESC – 2019 guidelines. A RiskFactor3 model combined CRP ≥ 3 mg/l, HbA1C ≥ 7%, and AlbU ≥ 30 mg/l. **Results:** No significant intergroup differences in OPG levels were observed. However, OPG was observably higher in women across both groups (T1D: 5.34 ± 1.2 pmol/l vs. 5.73 ± 1.83 pmol/l; controls: 5.06 ± 1.65 pmol/l vs. 6.16 ± 2.38 pmol/l, p < 0.05). In T1D patients, age (R² = 3%), disease duration (R² = 4.8%), and AlbU (R² = 3.9%) were significant positive determinants of OPG (p < 0.05). According to ESC-2019, 30.6% of T1D patients had high CVR and 69.4% had very high CVR. ST1RE classified 38.7% as low, 28.2% as moderate, and 33.1% as high CVR. ST1RE's AUC-ROC for males was 0.716 (p = 0.005) with a cut-off of 5.075 pmol/l, and for females, 0.683 (p = 0.039) with a cut-off of 5.355 pmol/l. For ESC-2019, the AUC-ROC for females was 0.644 (p = 0.102) with a cut-off of 5.025 pmol/l. **Conclusion:** OPG is a promising biomarker for assessing CVR in patients with long-standing T1D. Higher OPG levels in women and its associations with age, disease duration, and AlbU emphasize its potential prognostic role. Using ST1RE and ESC-2019, OPG effectively stratified patients by CVR. Incorporating OPG into clinical practice could improve early detection and personalized management of CVR in T1D patients.

Key words:

osteoprotegerin, long-standing type 1 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, cardiovascular risk, STENO Type 1 Risk Engine, ESC – 2019 guideline

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Резюме.

Въведение: Сърдечно-съдовите заболявания (ССЗ) са основно усложнение при пациенти с дългогодишен тип 1 захарен диабет (Т1ЗД), като остеопротегеринът (ОПГ) се разглежда като потенциален биомаркер за сърдечно-съдов риск (ССР). Настоящото проучване цели да оцени прогностичната стойност на ОПГ при пациенти с Т1ЗД,

използвайки STENO Type 1 Risk Engine (ST1RE) и ESC – 2019. **Материал и методи:** Настоящото проспективно проучване тип случай-контрола включва 183 участници: 124 с Т13Д (53.2% мъже на възраст 42.7 ± 10.4 години, продължителност на диабета 25.3 ± 8.2 години) и 59 здрави контроли (54.1% мъже, на възраст 45.1 ± 9.1 години). Серумните нива на ОПГ са определени с ELISA; CRP – имуно-турбидиметричен метод (Advia chemistry 1800); HbA1C (%) – имуно-инхибиционен анализ (ADVIA chemistry 1800); албумин в урина (AlbU) (mg/l) – имуно-турбидиметричен анализ (Olympus AU600). Инструменти за оценка на ССР: STENO Type 1 Risk Engine (ST1RE) и ESC – 2019. Моделът RiskFactor3 е конструиран като комбинация от: $CRP \geq 3$ mg/l, $HbA1C \geq 7\%$ и $AlbU \geq 30$ mg/l. **Резултати:** Не открихме значима междугрупова разлика в ОПГ, но и в двете групи ОПГ е отчетен по-висок при жените: Т13Д 5.34 ± 1.2 pmol/l срещу 5.73 ± 1.83 pmol/l и контролна група 5.06 ± 1.65 pmol/l срещу 6.16 ± 2.38 pmol/l, $p < 0.05$. Възрастта, продължителността на заболяването и AlbU са значими положителни детерминанти за ОПГ при пациентите с Т13Д: $R^2 = 3\%$ – възраст, $R^2 = 4.8\%$ – продължителност на Т13Д, $R^2 = 3.9\%$ – AlbU, $p < 0.05$. Според ESC – 2019, 30.6% от пациентите с Т13Д са с висок ССР, 69.4% – с много висок ССР; според ST1RE 38.7% от пациентите с Т13Д са с нисък, 28.2% – с умерен, и 33.1% – с висок ССР. Според ST1RE AUC-ROC за мъжете е 0.716 ($p = 0.005$), cut-off = 5.075 pmol/l (ДЧ 70.8%, ДС 55.9%); за жените – 0.683 ($p = 0.039$), cut-off = 5.355 pmol/l (ДЧ 66.7%, ДС 60%). Относно ESC-2019, AUC-ROC за жените е 0.644 ($p = 0.102$), cut-off = 5.025 pmol/l (ДЧ 70%, ДС 60%). **Заключение:** ОПГ е обещаващ биомаркер за оценка на ССР при Т13Д. Връзките на ОПГ с възрастта, продължителността на заболяването и AlbU подчертават неговото прогностично значение. Интегрирането на ОПГ в клиничната практика би могло да подобри ранната диагностика и персонализираното управление на ССР.

Ключови думи: остеопротегерин, дългогодишен захарен диабет тип 1, сърдечно-съдово заболяване, сърдечно-съдов риск, STENO Type 1 Risk Engine, ESC–2019

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is associated with an increased risk of CVD. Most recommendations for preventing CVD in T1D are derived from studies on type 2 diabetes (T2D) [1]. CVR calculation models for the general population and for patients with T2D do not account for risk factors (RFs) like hyperglycaemia, or the presence of microvascular complications, thus underestimating CVR in patients with T1D [1, 2, 3, 4]. In T1D, the reported relative risk of CVD, adjusted for age, is 4 to 10 times higher compared to the general population [5]. Management approaches to minimize the frequency of CVD in T1D are mainly extrapolated from T2D experience, and the pathophysiological mechanisms are not well understood. Increasing scientific developments are confirming the potential of new classes of laboratory biomarkers that characterize cardiovascular changes in patients with T1D.

Osteoprotegerin (OPG), also known as TNFRSF11B, is a key member of the tumor necrosis factor (TNF) receptor family, initially discovered for its critical role in bone metabolism and later identified in the vascular system [6]. This secretory glycoprotein, comprising 401 amino acids and capable of forming homodimeric structures, functions predominantly to inhibit osteoclastogenesis and has significant implications in cell differentiation, survival, and apoptosis, reflecting its broad biological importance [6]. OPG serves as a soluble decoy receptor for both the receptor activator of nuclear

factor kappa-B ligand (RANKL) and the apoptosis-inducing ligands, tumor necrosis factor (TNF) – related apoptosis – inducing ligand (TRAIL) [6, 7]. Regardless of its primary clinical significance in relation to its involvement in bone metabolism, the focus of the current study was on the atherogenic effects of the protein.

OPG emerges as a reliable laboratory marker with predictive value for CVD. The relationship between circulating OPG and cardiovascular RFs such as age, smoking, hypertension, insulin resistance, obesity, diabetes, renal impairment, and inflammatory conditions has been extensively described [6]. OPG serves as an indicator of cumulative exposure and the severity of known and emerging vascular RFs, reflecting the overall activity of the OPG/RANK/RANKL system [6, 7]. It's hypothesized that prolonged OPG overexpression triggers profibrotic, pro-inflammatory, pro-apoptotic, and plaque destabilizing properties [7, 8, 9]. In healthy individuals, the pro-atherogenic and anti-atherogenic effects of OPG are balanced, however, under constant induction by various RFs like chronic hyperglycaemia in diabetes, the pro-atherogenic pathway may dominate [10]. DM is associated with an increased risk of CVD as well as an increased risk of bone loss and osteoporosis progression [11, 12, 13]. The relationships between bone metabolism and T1D have been extensively studied in recent years. Pathologically elevated plasma OPG levels predict overall and cardiovascular mortality in diabetic complication patients [6, 11]. Moreover, elevated OPG levels have been observed in

patients with T1D, with a positive correlation between duration of T1D and biomarker levels, though mechanisms remain unclear [14, 15, 16].

This study aimed to assess the prognostic significance of OPG in CVR estimation among T1D patients using specific CVR assessment tools.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study population and design

The observation was a prospective case-control comparison type. A total of 183 participants (59 healthy volunteers and 124 patients with T1D) were included in this study, without any targeted selection. The project was carried out at the University Hospital "Saint Marina" – Varna, between 2018 and 2020. The research protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committee at Medical University – Varna, under Decision No. 72, dated March 1, 2018. Every patient signed informed written consent for the acceptance of participation in the study after explaining the procedures.

Inclusion criteria were as follows: individuals with over 15 years of T1D duration and healthy individuals matching in gender, age, and BMI.

Exclusion criteria were as follows: involvement in other clinical studies; significant mental or physical disabilities; over 3% body weight change in the last 3 months; recent vascular incidents; acute conditions during the study (except specific diabetic emergencies for T1D participants); pregnancy; and, for T1D subjects, recent severe hypoglycaemia or ketoacidosis and severe microvascular complications.

Laboratory analyses

Blood and urine samples were collected following standardized procedures. Blood for HbA1C analysis was drawn into K2EDTA tubes. For urine, first morning samples of 20 ml were collected, then centrifuged at 2500 G for 15 minutes for AlbU assessment. Serum for CRP and OPG tests was separated using a gel separator vacutainer and similarly centrifuged. OPG levels were determined by an ELISA kit (Human OPG ELISA, BioVendor, Czech Republic), CRP levels – by immuno-turbidimetric analysis on ADVIA Chemistry 1800 system, and HbA1C – by an immuno-inhibition method, standardized to DCCT/NGSP, presenting results as a percentage of total hemoglobin (measured colorimetrically on the same system). AlbU was analyzed by immuno-turbidimetry on Olympus AU600. Detection limits (LOD) and reference ranges (RR) were as follows: LOD_{CRP} = 0.04 mg/l (RR: 0-5 mg/l); LOD_{HbA1C} = 2% (RR: up to 6%), LOD_{AlbU} = 0.25 mg/l (RR: up to 20 mg/24h), and LOD_{OPG} = 0.03 pmol/l (RR: 4,1 ± 2,3 pmol/l).

The CVR evaluation tools utilized in this study included ST1RE and ESC Guidelines (2019). ST1RE cal-

culates 10-year non-fatal/fatal CVR, considering factors like gender, age, diabetes duration, CVD history, systolic blood pressure, AlbU, HbA1C, eGFR, LDL-cholesterol, smoking, and activity level. Categories: low (< 10%), moderate (10-20%), high (≥ 20%) CVR. Link: ST1RE Calculator. ESC Guidelines (2019) assess CVR based on age, gender, smoking, systolic blood pressure, and total cholesterol levels [17]. Categories: moderate – young T1D patients (< 35 years, < 10 years diabetes duration); high risk – diabetes duration > 10 years or other RFs; very high risk – diabetes with target organ damage, 3 major RFs, or early T1D onset (> 20 years).

A RiskFactor3 model was developed for individuals with diabetes, categorizing them based on common CVR factors: CRP levels (below and above 3 mg/l), glycaemic control (good: HbA1C below 7% and poor: HbA1C above 7%), and AlbU levels (normoalbuminuria – AlbU below 30 mg/l, microalbuminuria – AlbU between 30 and 300 mg/l, and macroalbuminuria – AlbU above 300 mg/l). Patients were grouped into: Group 0 (no RFs), Group 1 (1 RF), Group 2 (2 RFs), and Group 3 (all 3 RFs).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 19 software package (modified 21 May 2021; IBM Corp., Armonk, New York, United States) with Windows 7.0. software (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington, United States). Numerical data were presented as mean value ± standard deviation (SD). Descriptive statistics determined data central tendency and dispersion. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) assessed linear relationships between variables. Single and multiple linear regression examined independent and dependent variables. Factor analysis, independent-samples T-tests, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) identified significant mean differences. Nonparametric methods like Chi-square tested nominal data. Receiver – Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis and the area under the curve (AUC) calculation evaluated laboratory parameter sensitivity (Se) and specificity (Sp), establishing optimal cut-off values. A significance level (α) of 0.05 was maintained, p-values < 0.05 rejected the null hypothesis.

RESULTS

Clinical characteristics

The study comprised 59 healthy subjects and 124 patients with long-standing T1D. Gender distribution was similar between the groups, $\chi^2 = 0.118$, $p = 0.731$. Average age was 45.14 ± 9.17 years in the control group and 42.68 ± 10.40 years in the T1D group, with a non-significant difference ($t = 1.550$, $p = 0.123$). Mean duration of T1D was 25.31 ± 8.22 years, with a median of 24 years (Table 1).

Table 1. Baseline characteristics

Parameter	T1D subjects (N = 124)		Controls (N = 59)		P-value
	mean	SD	mean	SD	
Age (years)	42.68	10.4	45.14	9.17	0.123
Male	66 (53.2%)	/	33 (55.9%)	/	/
Duration of T1D (years)	25.31	8.22	/	/	/
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.71	4.11	24.88	3.81	0.313
CRP (mg/l)	3.56	9.3	2.57	3.76	0.433
HbA1C (%)	8.47	1.62	5.40	0.39	< 0.001
AlbU (mg/l)	63.72	147.38	12.22	19.88	0.009
OPG (pmol/l)	5.528	1.545	5.568	2.073	0.891

N – number; SD – standard deviation

Diabetic patients were categorized according to ESC-2019 guidelines: 30.6% had high CVR, and 69.4% had very high CVR, with no significant gender difference ($\chi^2 = 0.480$, $p = 0.489$). ST1RE classification revealed 38.7% with low CVR, 28.2% with moderate, and 33.1% with high CVR. A gender difference was significant: 39.6% of men and 60.4% of women had low CVR; 60% of men and 40% of women had high CVR; 63.4% of men and 36.6% of women had very high CVR ($\chi^2 = 5.943$, $p = 0.05$).

OPG – influence of gender, age and duration of diabetes

The women in both study groups showed higher mean OPG levels. In patients with T1D, the mean difference (MD) was 0.384 pmol/l with borderline statistical significance (men: 5.342 ± 1.996 pmol/l vs women: 5.726 ± 1.832 pmol/l), $p = 0.055$. In controls, the MD was significant: MD = 1.108 pmol/l, $p = 0.049$ (men: 5.056 ± 1.645 pmol/l vs women: 6.163 ± 2.378 pmol/l).

When comparing the average levels of OPG against the median duration of T1D, higher values were observed for individuals with a longer duration (5.723 ± 1.506 pmol/l) compared to those with a duration below 24 years (5.317 ± 1.574 pmol/l). The MD was 0.406 pmol/l, $t = -1,400$, $p = 0.164$. In the control group, a

weak negative correlation was observed between OPG and age ($r = -0.284$, $p = 0.038$), notably significant only among men ($r = -0.565$, $p = 0.001$). Conversely, in the T1D group, a less pronounced positive correlation was found between OPG and age with borderline statistical significance ($r = 0.173$, $p = 0.067$). The regression curves illustrating the dependencies between OPG and age, as well as OPG and the duration of diabetes in individuals with T1D, are shown (Fig. 1). The reported coefficients of determination are as follows: $R^2 = 3\%$, $p = 0.06$ concerning age, and $R^2 = 4.8\%$, $p = 0.019$ concerning the duration of diabetes.

OPG – associations with AlbU, CRP, HbA1C, and RiskFactor3

In individuals with long-standing T1D, average OPG levels were compared based on HbA1c levels below and above 7% (5.446 ± 1.4691 pmol/l and 5.541 ± 1.563 pmol/l), CRP levels below and above 3 mg/l (5.383 ± 1.557 pmol/l and 5.885 ± 1.499 pmol/l), and AlbU levels categorized as below 30 mg/l, between 30 and 300 mg/l, and above 300 mg/l (5.407 ± 1.423 pmol/l; 5.491 ± 1.848 pmol/l; and 6.937 ± 1.609 pmol/l). A significant difference was found in mean OPG levels between the groups matched vs AlbU ($F = 3.263$, $p = 0.042$). In the control group, the differences observed

Fig. 1. Dependencies between OPG and: age; duration of diabetes in individuals with T1D

in HbA1C, CRP, and AlbU were deemed insignificant. However, within the T1D group, a significant, but weak correlation was identified between OPG and AlbU ($r = 0.218$, $p = 0.021$). Conversely, in the control subjects, no significant correlations were observed. To establish the linear relationship between AlbU and OPG values in individuals with T1D, a single linear regression analysis was conducted ($F = 5.521$, $p = 0.021$) with an adjusted $R^2 = 3.9\%$, represented by the equation:

$$\text{OPG (pmol/l)} = 5.381 + 0.218 \times \text{AlbU (mg/l)}.$$

ANOVA analysis conducted on RiskFactor3 revealed a trend of elevation among males, albeit at a 90% CI. The mean OPG levels for males in each group were as follows: 4.93 ± 0.391 pmol/l for group 0, 5.092 ± 1.05 pmol/l for group 1, 5.565 ± 1.392 pmol/l for group 2, and 6.823 ± 0.567 pmol/l for group 3 ($F = 2.550$, $p = 0.065$). In females, the mean OPG levels were 5.004 ± 0.600 pmol/l for group 0, 5.828 ± 1.855 pmol/l for group 1, 5.445 ± 2.024 pmol/l for group 2, and 6.732 ± 1.663 pmol/l for group 3 ($F = 1.031$, $p = 0.387$). Additionally, OPG exhibited a positive but weak correlation with RiskFactor3 ($r = 0.194$, $p = 0.039$).

OPG – associations with ST1RE and ESC – 2019 Guidelines

Regarding ST1RE, OPG showed a positive but weak correlation with borderline statistical significance ($r = 0.183$, $p = 0.053$), and no significant relationship between OPG and ESC – 2019. Furthermore, there were no significant intergroup differences in mean OPG levels relative to both ST1RE ($F = 2.322$, $p = 0.103$) and ESC-2019 ($t = -1.003$, $p = 0.318$) as shown in Fig. 2. The median and interquartile range of OPG in men with low CVR according to ST1RE were 4.95 (4.31-5.86) pmol/l; in men with moderate CVR were 4.92 (4.04-5.37) pmol/l; in men at high risk were 5.775 (4.855-6.87) pmol/l; in women with low CVR were 5.73 (4.24-5.74) pmol/l; in moderate CVR were 5.60 (4.91-6.325) pmol/l; in high CVR were 6.25 (5.05-6.78) pmol/l (Fig. 2). The medians and interquartile ranges of OPG in men according to ESC – 2019 were: 5.12 (4.265-6.215) pmol/l for high risk and 5.20 (4.56-6.218) pmol/l for very high CVR. In women, they were the following: 4.82 (4.24-5.60) pmol/l for high risk and 5.425 (4.708-6.605) pmol/l for a very high CVR as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Mean OPG levels in males and females according to ST1RE

Fig. 3. Mean OPG levels in males and females according to ESC – 2019 guidelines

ROC analyses for determining cut-off OPG values

Regarding ST1RE, the AUC-ROC was 0.687 ($p = 0.001$), while in the ESC-2019 categories, it was 0.589 ($p = 0.138$). Notably, OPG did not demonstrate significant prognostic value relative to RiskFactor3, with an AUC of 0.520 ($p = 0.734$). For the purpose of distinguishing patients with high CVR according to ST1RE, a cut-off value of 5.315 pmol/l was derived for OPG, yielding a Se of 64.1% and Sp of 63.5%. The calculated likelihood ratios were LR+ = 1.75 and LR- = 0.57, with a diagnostic odds ratio (DOR) of 3.07. Additionally, the Youden index was -0.994, and the diagnostic effectiveness (DE) was 63.7% (Table 2, Fig. 4).

Furthermore, at ST1RE for males, the AUC-ROC was 0.716 ($p = 0.005$), and for females – 0.683 ($p = 0.039$). Regarding the ESC – 2019 guidelines, the AUC-ROC for males was 0.537 ($p = 0.650$), and for females - 0.644 ($p = 0.102$). For women with a very high CVR according to ESC – 2019, a cut-off value of OPG was derived as 5.025 pmol/l, with a Se of 70% and Sp

of 60%, LR+ = 1.75 and LR- = 0.571, and DOR = 3.064. The Youden index was -0.9, and DE was 67.2%.

Threshold OPG values for differentiation of persons with high CVR according to ST1RE were derived: 5.075 pmol/l with Se 70.8% and Sp 55.9% for men and 5.355 pmol/l for women with Se 66.7% and Sp 60%. The following were determined: LR+ = 1.605, LR - = 0.623, DOR = 2.576, Youden index = -0.851 and DE = 62% for men and LR+ = 1.668, LR - = 0.599, DOR = 2,784, Youden index = -0.933 and DE = 61.8% for women (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

The study found a notable difference in OPG concentration between genders, with women showing higher levels than men. This difference is particularly substantial before menopause. Serum OPG levels tend to converge after the age of 50, attributed to estrogen deficiency in women and testosterone's inhibitory effect in men [6, 18, 19]. In our study, where the

Table 2. Diagnostic accuracy for serum OPG levels, relative to ST1RE

Parameter	Criterion	cut-off	N	TP	TN	FP	FN	Se	Sp	DE
OPG (pmol/l)	ST1RE – high CVR	5.315	113	25	47	27	14	64.1%	63.5%	63.7%

TP – true positive, TN – true negative, FP – false positive, FN – false negative

Diagonal segments are produced by ties.

Fig. 4. AUC-ROC to estimate a prognostic value of OPG with T1D relative to ST1RE

Table 3. Diagnostic accuracy of OPG relative to ST1RE and ESC – 2019 guidelines for men and women with T1D

Parameter	Criterion	Cut-off value	N	TP	TN	FP	FN	Se	Sp	DE
OPG (pmol/l) Men	ST1RE – high CVR	5.075	58	17	19	15	7	70.8%	55.9%	62%
OPG (pmol/l) Women	ST1RE – high CVR	5.355	55	10	24	16	5	66.7%	60%	61.8%
OPG (pmol/l) Women	ESC-2019 – very high CVR	5.025	55	28	9	6	12	70%	60%	67.2%

TP – true positive, TN – true negative, FP – false positive, FN – false negative

average age was below 50, this gender difference was confirmed. Additionally, our findings support existing literature indicating that age and disease duration are significant positive determinants for serum OPG levels in patients with T1D [12, 16, 20]. Several studies have noted an increase in OPG concentrations with age [19]. The exact mechanisms underlying the relationship between OPG and age remain incompletely understood, although hypotheses include changes in bone metabolism, alterations related to glucose homeostasis, and vascular physiological changes. According to a meta-analysis (2020), the results on the relationship between the duration of the disease and serum OPG levels are contradictory: in some cases, it is positive, while others do not report any association [11]. For instance, Boyadzhieva M et al. (2013) found no analogous relationship between serum OPG levels and the duration of T2D [21]. Given these discrepancies, further research in this direction is warranted to elucidate the complex interplay between OPG levels, age, and disease duration in different types of diabetes.

In our study, we discovered a significant positive correlation between serum OPG levels and the proposed RiskFactor3 model. After conducting ANOVA analysis, we observed a noticeable difference, although it reached only at 90% CI, indicating a proportional increase in OPG values across different risk groups. Upon further examination by gender, we found a difference with borderline statistical significance (at 90% CI) only between group 1 and group 3 males. During the partial analysis of interactions between serum OPG levels and each variable included in RiskFactor3, a significant association with AlbU was identified. However, contrary to previous studies, we did not observe significant positive correlations between serum OPG levels and HbA1C% or CRP [11, 22, 23].

The current study's findings validate the well-established link between OPG and AlbU in diabetes, as documented in existing literature. In individuals with long-standing T1D, we observed a significant elevation in serum OPG levels, regarding the AlbU value. Elbana M et al (2022) and Perez de Cirza et al. (2015), have postulated a positive association between OPG and DN in T1D [23, 24]. Our study, reflecting prevalent poor glycaemic control in the majority of our cohort, underscores DN's pivotal role as a precursor to CVD development. Longitudinal studies by Gordin et al. (2013) involving nearly 2,000 adults with T1D over a decade identified OPG as an independent predictor of cardiovascular events [25]. Additionally, Jorsal et al. (2008) demonstrated serum OPG levels as an independent predictor of total and cardiovascular mortality in individuals with nephropathy [26]. This supports the hypothesis of OPG accumulation within arterial walls, contributing to generalized vascular changes and calcification

in long-standing T1D. Grauslund et al. (2010) reported significant OPG level variations between patients with macro-, microalbuminuria, and normoalbuminuria, particularly in cases with extended T1D duration [14]. Subsequent studies by Elsamahy et al. (2015), Wang et al. (2013), and Fekih et al. (2016) further corroborated these findings, showing significantly elevated OPG levels in patients with AlbU above 30 mg/24h compared to those with AlbU below 30 mg/24h [12, 22, 27]. In summary, our study reinforces the notion that OPG positively correlates with AlbU under conditions of poor glycaemic control, thus contributing to CVD development in individuals with long-standing T1D.

The current interdisciplinary study represents the first global assessment of the association between the biomarker OPG and established scales for CVR assessment in individuals with long-standing T1D. While a proportional trend of increasing serum OPG levels relative to the CVR category according to ST1RE and ESC-2019 was observed, it did not reach statistical significance. However, when considering gender differences, a significant difference was noted in the mean biomarker levels between males with low and high CVR, as well as between males with moderate and those with high CVR. Moreover, a significant positive correlation was identified between serum OPG and ST1RE, demonstrating a direct relationship and no significant association was found between OPG and ESC-2019. Thus, the results of the present study confirm the association of OPG with CVR in individuals with diabetes, particularly with respect to ST1RE. The reported correlations between the biomarker and several variables from ST1RE (including gender, age, duration of diabetes, AlbU, and glycaemic control) offer an explanation for the observed stronger association of OPG with ST1RE compared to ESC-2019. This finding supports the hypothesis proposed by Chalakov et al., suggesting that risk calculators assign different weights to various RFs, indicating the degree of contribution of each factor [28]. In contrast, ESC-2019 does not assign different weights to individual RFs, nor quantifies them, thus introducing subjectivity into the assessment process. Early studies by Browner et al. and Olesen et al. were among the first to establish the association between serum OPG levels and the progression of diabetic complications [29,30]. Gordin et al. (2013) identified the biomarker as an independent predictor of CVD in diabetes [25]. Subsequent research has consistently described the relationship between the severity of atherosclerotic plaques, CAD and serum OPG levels [10]. Numerous researchers have investigated OPG-associated mechanisms in the development of CVD and its prognostic role in diabetes [7]. High-risk populations such as patients with T1D and T2D have shown elevated OPG values compared to healthy controls with sig-

nificantly higher levels reported in individuals who have experienced cardiovascular events [7,11]. Conflicting data exist regarding the impact of statin treatment on circulating OPG levels in patients with very high CVR. Some studies have reported a decrease, while others have observed an increase, with variations even among different statin drugs [10]. For example, in the study by Boyadzhieva et al. (2013), individuals with newly diagnosed T2D exhibited similar serum OPG results regardless of the presence or absence of known CAD [21]. Those with confirmed CAD underwent standard statin therapy, which could potentially influence OPG levels and explain the lack of differences observed with the non-CAD group [21].

In a study by Raaz-Schrauder et al. (2017) involving 414 individuals with moderate CVR, as assessed by the Framingham Risk Score and ESC criteria, a notable correlation was uncovered between OPG levels and various atherogenic cytokines [16]. The precise role of OPG in the development of diabetic macroangiopathy remains incompletely understood. Despite this ambiguity, OPG continues to be linked with the progression of CVD. The origin of OPG expression remains a subject of debate. M. Boyadzhieva et al. (2013) identified a significant association between serum OPG levels and carotid intima-media thickness in men recently diagnosed with T2D [21]. This finding led the researchers to speculate that vascular changes might influence OPG regulation or that OPG could serve as a crucial regulatory molecule in the early stages of vascular dysfunction during the progression of diabetes [21].

The results of the applied ROC analysis against the established scales for the assessment of CVR in T1D demonstrated that OPG has a good prognostic value (approximately 70%) relative to ST1RE. The derived OPG cut-off values for males and females in differentiating high CVR according to ST1RE were 5.075 pmol/l for males and 5.355 pmol/l for females. Furthermore, for women using ESC – 2019, OPG also showed good prognostic value (approximately 65%), with a threshold value of 5.025 pmol/l. These findings suggest that OPG serves as a promising biomarker for assessing CVD risk in individuals with long-standing T1D, particularly in high-risk patients.

Study limitations

The present study is limited primarily by the relatively small sample size, which may compromise statistical power, particularly in sex-stratified analyses. In addition, several associations achieved only borderline statistical significance and should thus be interpreted as indicative trends rather than conclusive evidence. Furthermore, the absence of long-term follow-up restricts the ability to draw firm conclusions, especially regarding OPG levels and their putative contribution to

the progressive increase in cardiovascular risk among individuals with long-standing type 1 diabetes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study supports the notion that OPG is a promising biomarker for CVD assessment in individuals with long-standing T1D. The study found that OPG levels are higher in women, and factors such as age, disease duration and AlbU are positive determinants of OPG in T1D patients. Using ST1RE and ESC – 2019 guidelines, we demonstrated that OPG could effectively stratify patients by their CVR, with specific cut-off values providing reasonable Se and Sp. These results underscore that integrating of OPG into routine clinical laboratory practice could enhance CVR stratification and facilitate appropriate treatment strategies for T1D patients. We advocate for further research involving larger patient cohorts to validate these findings and elucidate the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms involved in CVD development in T1D.

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